

THE IMPORTANCE OF STRUCTURED OPENINGS AND CLOSINGS IN STORY WRITING

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Annotation. Writing a novel can feel like staring into the void. This article explores the importance of structured openings and closings in story writing.

Key words: blank page, openings, closings, narrative structure, plotting system, pre-existing blueprint.

Аннотация. Написание романа может ощущаться как взгляд в пустоту. В этой статье исследуется важность структурированных вступлений и заключений в написании рассказов.

Ключевые слова: чистая страница, начало, завершение, повествовательная структура, система построения сюжета, уже существующий план.

Introduction

When you're sitting in front of a blank page, anything could happen, and that feeling is both freeing and terrifying. This is where a good story structure comes in.

Experts say that limitless possibility might not actually be the best for your creative brain. Instead, setting limitations or having rules to follow—like a story structure—can give you a box to think outside of.

A story structure is basically a map to keep you from getting lost as you set off into the unknown. It identifies the key elements of dramatic plot in any story. Once you know the path, you can chart your course and then play in the blank space from Point A to Point B.

If you want help with novel writing, read my 12-step post on how to write a novel.

Narrative structure and plotting systems come in many forms, some more complex than others. These nine story structures range from the classic plot pyramid to the lesser-known plot embryo to Aristotle's ancient Poetics, but they're all trying to answer the same questions:

1. **What makes up a story?**
2. **What kind of stories please the reader?**
3. **What is it about a beginning, middle, and end that makes a plot really sing?**

By analyzing the structure and plot of our favorite stories, we can find out how they work and why we love them so much. Then, you can see what sparks your own creativity and use it as a guide on how to structure your own story.

Nine Story Structures to Consider:

1. **Classic Plot Pyramid (Freytag's Pyramid):** Introduced by Gustav Freytag, it includes exposition, rising action, climax, falling action, and resolution.
2. **Three-Act Structure:** A timeless structure that breaks down into Setup, Confrontation, and Resolution.
3. **Hero's Journey (Monomyth):** Popularized by Joseph Campbell, this structure includes stages like the Call to Adventure, Supreme Ordeal, and Return with the Elixir.
4. **Save the Cat! Beat Sheet:** Developed by Blake Snyder, it provides 15 "beats" or plot points for your story.
5. **Snowflake Method:** Created by Randy Ingermanson, it starts small with a single sentence and expands into more detailed summaries.
6. **Plot Embryo (Dan Harmon's Story Circle):** A simplified version of the Hero's Journey focusing on character transformation through eight steps.
7. **Seven-Point Story Structure:** Breaks down into Hook, Plot Turn 1, Pinch Point 1, Midpoint, Pinch Point 2, Plot Turn 2, and Resolution.
8. **Fichtean Curve:** Focuses on continuous rising action without a distinct beginning or end.
9. **Aristotle's Poetics:** The earliest known study of story structure, emphasizing a beginning, middle, and end with elements like Catharsis and Hamartia.

By exploring these structures, you can find the one that resonates with you, giving your novel a solid foundation and direction. Understanding these frameworks allows you to see how they fit together, guiding your story from inception to completion while still leaving room for creativity and unique expression.

Nothing makes the challenging task of crafting your first novel feel more attainable than adopting a story structure to help you plot your narrative. While using a pre-existing blueprint might make you worry about ending up with a formulaic, predictable story, you can probably analyze most of your favorite books using various narrative structures that writers have been using for decades (if not centuries)! This post will reveal seven distinct story structures that any writer can use to build a compelling narrative. But first... What is story

structure? Story structure is the order in which plot events are told to the reader or audience. While stories can be told in a wide variety of ways, most Western story structures commonly share certain elements: exposition, rising action, climax, falling action, and resolution. A tightly controlled structure will answer a reader's questions, provide a climax followed by resolution and information at the end of the story, further the characters' development, and unravel any central conflicts. In other words, it's responsible for a satisfying narrative experience that accomplishes the author's aims. Writing is an art, but if there's one part of the craft that's closer to science, this would be it. Become a master of story structure, and you will have the world at your feet.

Classic story structure

When people discuss different story structures, they often talk about the different frameworks used to analyze stories. When you boil them all down, all stories have certain shared elements. Elements of classic story structure: Exposition. This first part establishes a protagonist's normal life and greater desires, and usually culminates in the inciting incident. Rising action. The protagonist pursues their new goal and is tested along the way. Climax. Our hero achieves their goal — or so they think! Falling action. The hero now must deal with the consequences of achieving their goal. Resolution. The conclusion tying together the plot, character arcs, and themes. These are all common 'beats' to most stories. It can be easier to see these moments in genres with higher stakes (such as a military thriller), but you'll find them in almost any type of story. Even in something as seemingly mild as a rural romance, there will be rising action as our heroes tentatively fall in love and an all-is-lost moment where it seems like they will never get together (before they inevitably do). Without these steps, there is no conflict and no story — merely a series of events that will struggle to keep a reader interested.

Structure

Introduction. The status quo is established; an inciting incident occurs. Rise, or rising action. The protagonist actively pursues their goal. The stakes heighten. Climax. A point of no return, from which the protagonist can no longer go back to the status quo. Return, or fall. In the aftermath of the climax, tension builds, and the story heads inevitably towards... Catastrophe. The protagonist is brought to their lowest point. Their greatest fears have come true. This structural model is less frequently used in modern storytelling, partly due to readers' limited appetite for tragic narratives (although you can still spot a few tragic heroes in popular literature today). By and large, commercial fiction, films,

and television will see a protagonist overcome their obstacles to find some small measure of success. That said, it's still useful to understand the Pyramid as a foundational structure in Western literature — and you will still see it occasionally in the most depressing contemporary tales.

Conclusion

A great opening in a novel is incredibly important and should be taken seriously. It sets the tone for the entire story, and it can make or break a reader's interest from the start.

An effective opening will have characters that readers can relate to, an engaging plotline, vivid description of setting, and clever dialogue. Put simply – craft your opening thoughtfully and carefully for maximum impact.

References:

1. Kojkov V.V. Ispol'zovanie fakticheskikh dannyh pri prinjatii upravlencheskih reshenij v sfere zdavoohranenija (The use of evidence in decision-making in health care) [in Russian]. Menedzher zdavoohranenija Respubliki Kazakhstan. 2015; 2 (15): 68-78.
2. But U.K., Kolomb G.Dzh., Uil'jam Dzh. M. Issledovanie: Shestnadcat' urokov dlja nachinajushhih avtorov (Research: Sixteen Lessons for Beginners) [in Russian]. M., 2004: 92.
3. James C. Boyd, Nader Rifai, Thomas M. Annesley. Preparation of Manuscripts for Publication: Improving Your Chances for Success. Clinical Chemistry. 2009; 55(7):1259-1264.
4. Kulmagambetov I.R., Kojkov V.V. How to prepare' kachestvennuju nauchnuju publikaciju? (How to prepare a high-quality scientific publication?) [in Russian]. Densaulyq saqtaudy damytu zhurnaly. 2012; 1(61):76-86.
5. Kojkov V.V., Syzdykova A.A., Ospanova A.K., Z.B. Sultanova. Indikatory science i innovacionnoj dejatel'nosti kak kljuchевой mehanizm dostizhenija konkurentosposobnosti organizacij medicinskoj nauki i obrazovanija (Indicators of scientific and innovative activity as a key mechanism for achieving competitiveness of organizations of medical science and education) [in Russian]. Densaulyq saqtaudy damytu zhurnaly. 2013; 3 (68): 55-73.
6. Yusupova, M. J. (2023). YANGI O 'ZBEKISTON YOSHLARIDA VANANPARVARLIKNI TARBIYALASH DOLZARB PEDAGOGIK MUAMMO SIFATIDA. SCHOLAR, 1(16), 180-188.
7. Jalgasbaevna, Y. M. (2023). YANGI O 'ZBEKISTON YOSHLARIDA VATANPARVARLIKNI TARBIYALASH DOLZARB PEDAGOGIK MUAMMO SIFATIDA. Science and innovation, 2(Special Issue 13), 646-650.

8. Юсупова, М. Ж. (2023). ПАТРИОТИЧЕСКОЕ ВОСПИТАНИЕ МОЛОДЁЖИ НА ОСНОВЕ НАЦИОНАЛЬНЫХ ЦЕННОСТЕЙ–ЗАЛОГ УСПЕШНОГО РАЗВИТИЯ ОБЩЕСТВА. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(4 SPECIAL), 866-877.

9. SCImago Institutions Rankings. SCImago Research Group, 2016. Available at URL: <http://www.scimagojr.com>

